

**DIFFICULTIES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN TEACHING ORAL SPEECH
BASED ON CREATIVE TASKS**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ijodiy topshiriqlar va ulardan og'zaki nutqni o'stirishda foydalanish jarayonida o'qituvchida yuzaga keladigan qiyinchiliklar va imkoniyatlar haqida, ijodiy topshiriqlarni dars jarayoniga tadbiq qilishda darsning samaradorligi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: topshiriq, dars, dars jarayoni, nutq, nutq o'stirish, og'zaki nutq, o'qitish usullari.

Abstract: This article discusses the challenges and opportunities for teachers in the process of using creative tasks and their use in oral speech development, and the effectiveness of the lesson in implementing creative tasks in the classroom.

Keywords: assignment, lesson, teaching process, speech, speech development, oral speech, teaching methods.

During the years of independence, the education sector has been radically renewed, a great experience has been gained in the practical application of advanced methods and methods of training. Today, the world is evolving at a rapid pace. It has become a requirement of the times to approach the teaching of general education subjects based on the requirements of the time, to use the most advanced technologies in education. As the foundation of general secondary education, foreign language education is one of the main components that ensure the future development of students. It is known that many psychological aspects of a person, including his thinking, his culture, in particular, the positive or negative characteristics of his speech habits, are recognized by everyone at this age[1].

Therefore, it is necessary to pay very serious attention to the content, form and means of foreign language education, to avoid mistakes and shortcomings. In particular, the elements of public speaking that are instilled in students during school years create a solid foundation for them to become highly cultured individuals in the future [2].

Currently, there is a growing interest and attention to the use of innovative pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process. One of the main reasons for this is that while in traditional education, students are taught only to

master the importance of using ready-made knowledge in creative tasks, in foreign language education, modern technologies teach them to search for the knowledge they have acquired, to study independently, to analyze it, and even to draw their own conclusions[3]. In this process, the teacher, along with the development, formation, education and training of the person, also focuses on the formation of speech skills and creates conditions.

Creative assignments increase the quality and effectiveness of the educational process, form the independent thinking process of students. It increases the enthusiasm and interest of students in the study of the subject, strengthens the knowledge, develops skills and skills, and freely uses them in practice.

Pedagogical technology refers to the new innovative methods and techniques that are being introduced into the field of education, from creative assignments used in the classroom, but also to the art and skill of implementing the educational function of pedagogical technology, which is the basis for the development of knowledge, skills and skills of students on the basis of very convenient methods. So the creative tasks are broad in scope it's a comprehensive concept that is very important in the formation of speech skills in the educational process [4].

Improving the quality and effectiveness of primary education in all public schools requires the introduction of modern pedagogical, innovative and information technologies into the educational process, the popularization of advanced work practices [5]. The main tasks of innovation and information technologies for the use of creative assignments in the teaching of foreign languages in practical lessons are:

- General, integrated development of the process of oral speech development of schoolchildren;
- Identification of specific goals and tasks to be solved in the process of oral speech development;
- Development of the content of the improvement of the oral speech development process of the use of creative assignments;
- Creating certain conditions for the free and independent activity of the learner during the lesson, as well as the formation of skills and qualifications;
- Organization of monitoring and evaluation of regular activities of students in language learning;
- Use of scientific and technical progress for the practical application of creative tasks used for the development of oral speech in the educational process.

The use of innovative methods, creative assignments and information technologies in improving the knowledge of schoolchildren provides the opportunity to:

- Activation of learning activities of students, improvement of the quality of learning material and efficiency of education;
- Differential approach to students with different levels of preparation and high aesthetic level of organization of classes (music, animation)
- Development of students' ability to select information flows in the environment, the transition from a method of visual expression to a type of practical activity, in this way the student becomes a subject of the learning process.

As a result of the formation of necessary skills in schoolchildren, raising the quality and effectiveness of creative assignments to a new level in the development of the student's knowledge in English lessons, introduction of modern methods of teaching, interactive methods and methods, advantages of various forms are achieved:

- The positive attitude of the child to learning the language helps in the formation of such skills as working with various information, logical and creative thinking, self-management, self-control in the group, mastering the rules of written and oral speech culture, organization of educational activities through reading skills, which are most necessary today[6].
- It allows teachers to work on themselves on a regular basis. They're always ready for the lesson. The classes are organized in an unconventional way. The efficiency of the students' learning is increased. It helps to fill in the gaps with the space separators. It enables the teacher to work collaboratively with the parents.
- Increased interest in learning a language, higher reading scores. It's not hard to do homework, it allows you to learn new topics even if you miss classes, it teaches you to think independently, freely. In the next stage, the desire to learn increases, and the interaction with adults and peers improves.
- Parents will have the right perspective on how to help their children at home and improve their schooling. Textbooks play an important role in forming the speech culture and skills of schoolchildren in language learning on an equal footing. First of all, the textbook materials should have a rich potential for the formation of speech culture, be able to engage the student with their impact, and secondly, when working on language materials, the study assignments should be aimed at directing the

students to speech activities. In the field of education, the introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies is helping to improve the quality of learning, one of the advanced pedagogical technologies is the technology of using creative assignments in practical lessons.

Creative assignment technologies were also used in the development of a methodology for the formation of oral communication skills of students, taking into account the age characteristics of the students. G. K. According to Selevko's definition, the technology of using creative tasks in the classroom is a type of activity in the context of situations aimed at the creation and assimilation of social experience, in which the independent control of behavior is formed, i.e. the student overcomes the timidity, inability to express himself, and many other such defects in speech in the form of language learning, and along with his oral speech, all language learning skills are formed and improved [7].

Creative assignment technologies for the formation of oral speech skills in students, as well as speech culture, are considered as a means of creating educational environments, and are implemented by students writing letters on their own behalf, but in a specific imaginary situation in which the student is forced to perform a specific role given by the teacher. You can also learn English by doing interactive exercises.

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